

Dynamics of low-mass galaxies over cosmic time with MUSE

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with (main) contributions from

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Context

The **dark matter** skeleton of the universe is now quite **well reproduced** with simulations

But how **baryons** cool down into DMH to **build galaxies** is still largely **unknown**

How did galaxies grow over time?

← Cosmic Time

High-z galaxies under the IFU microscope

High-z galaxies under the IFU microscope

But, **pre-selected** and mainly **massive** ($> 10^{10} M_{\text{sun}}$) **galaxies!**

MUSE
multi unit spectroscopic explorer

A wide-field IFU for deep surveys

Main advantages

- **No pre-selection**
 - blind surveys
 - high potential for discoveries
- **Broad spectral range @ high resolution**
 - physical properties
- **High throughput**
($\sim 3 \times 10^{-19}$ erg/s/cm² in 100h)
 - cosmic web, faint/low-mass galaxies
- **Wide Field-of-View**
 - statistics, environment

MUSE-HDFS: our 1st gold mine for galaxy evolution studies

MUSE – 27 hours

FWHM ~ 0.65'' – $F_{\text{lim}} = 10^{-19} \text{ ergs}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ arcsec}^{-2}$

189 redshifts up to $l_{\text{AB}} \sim 29.5$

Bacon+15

Resolved galaxies in MUSE-HDFS

Spatially-resolved galaxies
Galaxy size > 2 x PSF

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Probing distant & low-mass galaxies

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A sample of **lower-mass/SFR galaxies** compared with previous IFU surveys

Gas kinematics

Tully-Fisher relation

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Morphology from HST using GALFIT
 Gas kinematics from strong emission
 lines + 2D and GALPAK^{3D} disk
 modeling

Most of **low-mass ($< 10^{9.5} M_{\odot}$) galaxies** follow the TFR, but higher dispersion

Gas kinematics

Angular momentum

$$J^* = 2 \times R_d \times V_{\max}$$

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Gas kinematics

Angular momentum

$$J^* = 2 \times R_d \times V_{\max}$$

« **Grow-then-drop** » scenario for angular momentum evolution?

Stellar kinematics

Guérou+17, A&A submitted

17 galaxies at $0.2 < z < 0.8$

Star (and gas) kinematics using pPXF

- Indo-US stellar library (Valdes+04)
- Adaptive Voronoï binning at $\text{SNR} > 8$
- Full spectral fitting including **strong absorption lines** (CaK, Mgb, Fe, ...)

Stellar kinematics

Stellar kinematics

- **Good agreement** between **star** and **gas** kinematics
- **Gas** kinematics is a **good tracer of the gravitational potential**
- **Full dynamical model**, including dark matter, is **ongoing**

Conclusions

Galaxy Evolution with MUSE Deep Surveys

- **Added value** wrt **deep imaging** (eg. HST), **multi-slit spectroscopy** (eg. VIMOS, MOSFIRE), and/or **multi-IFU** (eg. KMOS)
- High sensitivity & no pre-selection → **low-mass galaxies**
- **Statistics** is being achieved now with the **full UDF coverage with MUSE** at 10-hours depth

Thanks!